

*EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR
MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS*

*THE DESCRIPTION OF THE
ECMWF/TOGA EXTENSION DATA SET*

1994

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PART I Description of the ECMWF/TOGA Extension Data Set

ECMWF has created and maintains an archive of Level III-A Atmospheric Data in support of projects associated with the World Climate Research Program (WCRP). It is intended that this archive eventually accommodates the 10 year period beginning 1 January 1985, fulfilling ECMWF's role as a Tropical Ocean and Global Atmosphere (TOGA) Level III Atmospheric Data Centre.

The ECMWF/TOGA Extension Data Set has been created to supplement the data available from the ECMWF/WCRP Data Archive. this data set is based on forecast data from the ECMWF model.

The data set is currently maintained using the WMO FM 92-IX Ext GRIB (grid in binary) form of data representation, with the non-standard version of GRIB Table 2 (see Appendix A). All fields are global within the data set.

A full extraction service is supported, enabling users to obtain sub-areas of data and data at various resolutions on regular Gaussian or lat/long grids. All extracted data are delivered using the GRIB representation.

The data set contains 24-hour forecast values at the resolution of the forecast system in operational use at ECMWF. Since the resolution and internal representation of the data set may vary according to changes in ECMWF's operational practice, data services associated with this data set include the interpolation to requested resolutions and representation forms.

The **Extension Data Set** is comprised as follows:

- period supported: 1 January 1991 to current date;
- fields are 24-hour accumulated forecast values based on the 12 to 36-hour forecasts (see Appendix B);
- each parameter is stored as a field of grid point values, in latitude rows starting at the north and working southwards; within each row values run from west to east starting at the 0° meridian;
- internal data is represented on a N80 Gaussian grid (80 lines of latitude, located according to a Gaussian distribution between the Pole and the Equator for each hemisphere, with a regular spacing of 1.125° between points along each latitude row) for the period 1 January 1991-17 September 1991, and on a N160 Gaussian grid (160 lines with 0.5625° between points along each row) thereafter;
- data are stored in FM 92 GRIB using sufficient bits to ensure that the grid point values can be retrieved to an accuracy consistent to the generating methods used;
- production of the archive has been made as automatic as possible using techniques which enable the data set to be updated daily.

The **Extension Data Set** contains:

surface sensible heat flux
surface latent heat flux
surface thermal radiation
surface solar radiation
top thermal radiation
top solar radiation
East-West surface stress
North-South surface stress
total precipitation.

PART II Requests for Data

In addition to providing the computer resources to set up and update this global data set, ECMWF provides a service in extracting reasonable sub-sets of the data (including sub-areas).

The data, together with software to unpack FM 92 GRIB will be supplied on IBM tapes or cartridges or 8 mm Exabyte cartridges. A fee (in pounds sterling or US-Dollars) will be charged to cover the data extraction and data interpolation (if required), the provision of tapes/cartridges, the processing of the request, and the dispatch to the user by air mail. These charges are "marginal costs" and ECMWF does not accept any liability for errors or omission in the data, or for any loss or damage arising from its use. However, users may report back to ECMWF any problems they encounter reading or using the data. To ensure that the fee charged reasonably reflects the processing required, the following formula is used:

$$\text{COST} = \alpha N (1 + \beta) + \alpha \gamma M + \alpha \delta T$$

- where α is the "unit cost" (currently £90)
- N is the number of data units to be written
(1 data unit = 150 megabytes)
- T is the number of tapes or cartridges to be written
- β is 0 if interpolation is NOT required
 1 if interpolation IS required
- γ is 1/12
- M is the number of months or part months comprising the period for which data are requested.
- δ = 1 for 1600 bpi tapes
 0 for other media.

This charge will remain in force until 31 December 1994.

Note that this cost is based on 4 component parts:

- αN to cover the cost of providing tapes/cartridges, handling, mail and basic extraction
- $\alpha \beta N$ to cover the extensive processing costs required to interpolate data and/or to convert from spectral to grid point
- $\alpha \gamma M$ to cover the processing costs involved in accessing data within the archive; this cost is greater for the high resolution data than for the basic data set, reflecting the magnitudes of the respective volumes of those data within the archive.
- $\alpha \delta T$ to cover additional tapes, handling and mail for low density media.

Note also that, in the context of the above, "interpolation" is defined as:

- * converting Gaussian grid point data to regular latitude/longitude, **or**

- * converting grid point data to any resolution other than that used to store the data within the archive.

Requests from each data set are processed and costed separately. Note that the number of tapes/cartridges required will depend on the amount of data, block length etc. requested.

Requests for data have to be made using the standard order forms, using one form for each request. An order form for each data set is included at the back of this brochure. All options are pre-defined and must be selected by marking the boxes on the form.

A user can define:

- * the time interval;
- * sub-areas based on regular rectangular areas with edges along latitude and longitude lines (such areas will be processed as minimum required areas, extra values outside the area specified may be supplied);
- * fields selected by parameter and (if appropriate) level;
- * representation and resolution (for the Advanced Operational Analysis and Supplementary Fields Data Sets only).

Data will be delivered on unlabelled IBM 3420 9-track magnetic tapes written at 1600 or 6250 bpi or on unlabelled IBM 3480 18-track magnetic cartridges written at 38,000 bpi or on 8 mm Exabyte cartridge. Each request will be delivered on tapes/cartridges. GRIB decoding software will be supplied as the first file on at least one of the tapes/cartridges.

Whenever possible, and unless the user specifies otherwise on the order form, IBM 3420 tapes will be packed in transit cases to prevent the tapes being damaged during delivery. All customers are requested to return the blue security transit cases as soon as possible to the address given below. Any tapes that appear to be faulty or that cannot be read for any reason should be returned in the transit cases. A charge of £100 will be made for each transit case not returned unless special arrangements are made in advance. Transit cases should be returned to:

Tape Library
E C M W F
Shinfield Park
Reading/Berks.
RG2 9AX
UNITED KINGDOM

The GRIB decoding software will be supplied at no extra charge. The file containing the software, written in FORTRAN 77 with some C routines for the SUN version, will contain 80 byte records within 800 byte, fixed length blocks.

Data will be written to IBM tapes and cartridges with fixed length tape blocks with a maximum tape block size equal to or less than either 32,768 bytes, or a value requested by the user. Tape block sizes will be computed according to the field lengths of the data requested, to maximise the use of the tape/cartridge. Each GRIB message will begin at the beginning of a tape block. Details of tape block lengths will be supplied with each set of data extracted.

Data will be written to 8 mm Exabyte tapes as one or more archive files. Each archive file will contain one data file up to 50 Megabytes in size. Archive

files will be written to tape sequentially using the UNIX 'tar' command so that individual files can be extracted as required.

The "unit cost", α , will be 90 pounds sterling, and the costing formula described above will be applied. Tapes/cartridges will be dispatched to users by air mail only - no arrangements will be entered into with third party carriers.

The minimum charge for any order from this data set is 180 pounds sterling.

Discounts will be given for large orders as follows:

orders in excess of £ 1,500	-	10% of that part of the normal charge which exceeds £1,500
orders in excess of £ 5,000	-	£350, plus 20% of that part of the normal charge which exceeds £5000
orders in excess of £10,000	-	£1,350, plus 25% of that part of the normal charge which exceeds £10,000.

To get a costing for the supply of data, the appropriate order form should be completed and returned to ECMWF. Extraction of data will commence as soon as confirmation of the order is received. An invoice will be sent shortly after the tapes containing the requested data have been dispatched. Requests for data should be addressed to:

The Director
E C M W F
Shinfield Park
Reading/Berks.
RG2 9AX
UNITED KINGDOM

Please note that according to the ECMWF Council rules governing the provision of data, organisations within the Member States are requested to contact their national meteorological service, whose written approval is required before ECMWF can commence extracting data for the order.

The cost charged for the supply of ECMWF data to organisations within the Member States may vary from the cost given by the formula on page 3, depending on the charging policy of the national meteorological services.

The Member States are as follows: Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Spain, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Yugoslavia, The Netherlands, Norway, Austria, Portugal, Switzerland, Finland, Sweden, Turkey, United Kingdom.

APPENDIX A

SUMMARY OF ECMWF VERSION OF TABLE 2 FOR WMO FM 92-IX EXT. GRIB

(This Table is used instead of Table 2 of FM 92-IX Ext. GRIB)

FIELD CODE	FIELD NAME	UNITS
146	Surface sensible heat flux*	*Wm ⁻²
147	Surface latent heat flux*	*Wm ⁻²
176	Surface solar radiation*	*WM ⁻²
177	Surface thermal radiation*	*Wm ⁻²
178	Top solar radiation*	*Wm ⁻²
179	Top thermal radiation*	*Wm ⁻²
180	E-W surface stress*	*Nm ⁻²
181	N-S surface stress*	*Nm ⁻²
228	Total precipitation*	m

* all fields contain accumulated values

**ORDER FORM FOR ECMWF/TOGA
EXTENSION DATA SET**

Name: _____
Organisation: _____
Address: _____

Telephone Number: _____
Facsimile Number: _____
Email Address: _____
Telex: _____

Please indicate which category given below nearest describes the organisation, and the users, which will use the data and give further information where appropriate:

- Member State National Meteorological Service
- Non-Member State National Meteorological Service.
- Government body / institute active or with interests in the meteorological field.
- Other non-profit seeking organisation; please state main source of funds below.*
- Commercial
- International organisation; please state main agency below.*

* Specify main source of funds or main agency as appropriate: _____

Please indicate which machine(s) you will be using to read and decode the data in order to help us determine which version of the software package to deliver:

- CRAY
- VAX
- IBM RS6000
- SUN
- SGI
- Other; please specify: _____

Please complete the remainder of the form according to your requirements:

OUTPUT FORMAT: All data will be supplied in FM 92 GRIB, on IBM tape or cartridge or EXABYTE tape. Data written to IBM tapes will be written with fixed length tape blocks, each GRIB message beginning with a new tape block. Tape block lengths will be 30,000 bytes or less.

Max. block length in bytes for IBM tapes /cartridges:

--	--	--	--	--	--

MEDIA: IBM 3420 Tape (1600 bpi)*

(select one option) IBM 3420 Tape (6250 bpi)*

IBM 3480 Cartridge (18-track)

8mm EXABYTE Cartridge

* Unless an 'X' is entered in the adjacent box, IBM 3420 tapes will be dispatched in transit boxes to reduce the risk of damage to the tapes. ECMWF requires that these boxes be returned at the customer's expense.

--

DATA TYPE: Forecast data

DATES: Start date (YYMMDD)

End date (YYMMDD)

ANALYSIS TIME: 1200 UTC

AREA: Select EITHER the whole globe:

--

OR a sub-area:

northern latitude**				•				
western longitude**				•				
southern latitude**				•				
eastern longitude**				•				

**For latitudes, + represents north, - represents south of the equator; for longitudes + represents east, - represents west of the 0 degree meridian.

REPRESENTATION/RESOLUTION:

(select one option)

Lat/long grid

☐
☐

Gaussian grid

grid length

<input type="text"/>	•	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
			<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

degs.¹

number of latitudes, N

2&4

PARAMETERS:

Total precipitation⁵

Surface sensible heat flux⁵

Surface latent heat flux⁵

Surface solar radiation⁵

Surface thermal radiation⁵

Top solar radiation⁵

Top thermal radiation⁵

U-component of surface stress⁵

V-component of surface stress⁵

☐

Notes:

- ¹ For a lat/long grid, the grid length which represents the model resolution is 1.125° for the period 1/1/91 to 16/9/91; and 0.5625° thereafter. From 17/9/91, data may be extrapolated to a lat/long grid with grid length 0.5°.
- ² For a Gaussian grid, the number of latitude lines between a pole and the equator is required: the model resolution is N80 for the period 1/1/91 to 16/9/91; and N160 thereafter. Data will not be extrapolated to higher resolutions
- ⁴ Software to interpolate data to a lat/long grid cannot be supplied by ECMWF.
- ⁵ Fields contain values which have been accumulated over 24 hours based on the HH+12 and the HH+36-hour forecasts.

Data are supplied by ECMWF subject to the following conditions:

1. The supplied data will not be supplied in whole or in part to any third party without the authorisation of ECMWF.
2. Articles, papers, or written scientific works of any form, based in whole or in part on data supplied by ECMWF, will contain an acknowledgement concerning the supplied data. The data may be cited as follows: "ECMWF 1994. The Description of the ECMWF/WCRP Level III-A Global Atmospheric Data Archive."
3. Although every care has been taken in preparing and testing the data, ECMWF cannot guarantee that the data are correct in all circumstances; neither does ECMWF accept any liability whatsoever for any error or omission in the data, or for any loss or damage arising from its use.
4. Access to the data is restricted to the scientists within the organisation of the data recipient, working on the same computer installation.
5. The recipient of the data will accept responsibility for informing all data users of these conditions.

This is to certify that I/we agree to the above conditions with respect to the supply of data by ECMWF.

Signed: _____ Date: _____

Payment is preferred in pounds sterling. The invoice will be in £ sterling, with the equivalent in US\$.

Please note that according to the ECMWF Council rules governing the provision of data, organisations within the Member States are requested to contact their national meteorological service, whose written approval is required before ECMWF can commence extracting data for the order.

For ECMWF internal use only

Date of order received/confirmed

Number of IBM tapes/cartridges supplied

Number of Exabyte tapes supplied

Amount charged for order

Invoice number

Budget reference

a) Authorised _____
Department Head Date

b) Approved _____
Financial Comptroller Date